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Sea Turtle Interaction Report

Data Set (DS) | Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:22313 | Updated: August 9, 2022 |

Published / External

COMPLETION RUBRIC

74%

26 / 35

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Short Citation:

Pacific Islands Regional Office, 2026: Sea Turtle Interaction Report, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/22313>.

[Full Citation Examples](#)

Item Identification

Title: Sea Turtle Interaction Report

Short Name: Sea Turtle Interaction Report

Status: In Work

Abstract: The Sea Turtle Interaction Report is a report sent out in pdf format to authorized individuals that summarizes sea turtle interactions in the longline fishery. The report is broken down by specific fishery such as deep set, shallow set and American Samoa and list certain details of every sea turtle interactions. There are two types of reports that are generated and referred to as 2(b) and 2(d). The 2(b) report is sent out whenever an unconfirmed sea turtle interaction has been called in by an observer out at sea. The 2(d) report is sent out on or around the the 1st and the 15th of every month.

Purpose: The purpose of the Sea Turtle Interaction Report is to provide real time and up-to-date information on sea turtle interactions in the longline fisheries.

Keywords

Theme Keywords

Thesaurus

Keyword

UNCONTROLLED

PARR Exclusion	Non-Environmental Data
None	confirmed
None	declared trip type
None	disposition
None	entangled
None	floatline length
None	green sea turtle
None	hawksbill sea turtle
None	hook number
None	hooked
None	leatherback sea turtle
None	loggerhead sea turtle
None	olive ridley sea turtle
None	sea turtle
None	set number
None	species code
None	trip coverage
None	trip number
None	turtle
None	type of interaction
None	unconfirmed

Temporal Keywords

Thesaurus

Keyword

UNCONTROLLED

None

begin set date

None

date of interaction

Spatial Keywords

Thesaurus

Keyword

UNCONTROLLED

None

Southern Pacific Ocean

Physical Location

Organization: Pacific Islands Regional Office

City: Pago Pago

State/Province: AS

Data Set Information

Data Set Scope Code: Data Set

Data Set Type: Files

Maintenance Frequency: Every Other Week

Data Presentation Form: Document (digital)

Support Roles

Data Steward

Date Effective From: 2018-10

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Harman, Robert

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: bob.harman@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5170

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Distributor

Date Effective From: 2018-10

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Harman, Robert

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: bob.harman@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5170

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Metadata Contact

Date Effective From: 2016-12

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Miller, Morgan

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: morgan.miller@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5116

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

Metadata Contact

Date Effective From: 2016-05

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Forney, Eric

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: eric.forney@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5103

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact Instructions:	Phone or email
------------------------------	----------------

Originator	CC ID: 177021
Date Effective From:	2006-04
Date Effective To:	
Contact (Organization):	Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)
Address:	1845 Wasp Boulevard, Bldg 176 Honolulu, HI 96818 USA

Point of Contact	CC ID: 837480
Date Effective From:	2018-10
Date Effective To:	
Contact (Person):	Harman, Robert
Address:	1845 Wasp Boulevard Honolulu, HI 96818 USA
Email Address:	bob.harman@noaa.gov
Phone:	808-725-5170
Contact Instructions:	Phone or email

Point of Contact	CC ID: 837484

Date Effective 2016-12

From:

Date Effective
To:

Contact
(Person): Miller, Morgan

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: morgan.miller@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5116

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact
Instructions: Phone or email

Point of Contact

CC ID: 837483

Date Effective 2016-05
From:

Date Effective
To:

Contact
(Person): Forney, Eric

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: eric.forney@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5103

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact
Instructions: Phone or email

Point of Contact

CC ID: 177022

Date Effective 2006-04
From:

Date Effective
To:

Contact (Person): Busscher, Kevin

Address: 1845 Wasp Boulevard
Honolulu, HI 96818
USA

Email Address: kevin.busscher@noaa.gov

Phone: 808-725-5102

Fax: 808-725-5217

Contact Instructions: Phone or email

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Extents

Extent Group 1

Extent Group 1 / Geographic Area 1

CC ID: 177025

Description Southern Pacific Ocean

Extent Group 1 / Time Frame 1

CC ID: 177026

Time Frame Type: Continuing

Start: 2006-04

Access Information

Security Class: Sensitive

Data Access Policy: Access is restricted to authorized individuals who have submitted a signed non-disclosure agreement and are approved to be on email list. This non-disclosure agreement must be renewed on an annual basis.

Data Access Procedure: Contact Operations Coordinator.

Data Access Constraints: Only individuals with a signed non-disclosure agreement on file and approved to be on the email list may access these data.

Data Use Constraints: Data must not be shared with non-authorized individuals.

Technical Environment

Description: pdf

Data Quality

Accuracy: Not Applicable

Completeness Report: Not Applicable

Quality Control Procedures Employed: Proof read

Data Management

Have Resources for Management of these Data Been Identified?: Yes

Approximate Percentage of Budget for: Unknown

these Data

Devoted to

☰ **Data**

Management:

Do these Data Comply with the Data Access Directive?:

No

Is Access to the Data Limited Based on an Approved Waiver?:

Yes

If Distributor (Data Hosting Service) is Needed, Please Indicate:

Not Applicable

Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Dissemination:

Immediate - once finalized disseminated to authorized individuals

Actual or Planned Long-Term Data Archive Location:

Other

If World Data Center or Other, Specify:

PIRO Network

Approximate Delay Between Data Collection and Archiving:

Not Applicable

How Will the Data Be

Daily backup PIRO-IT

**Protected from
Accidental or
Malicious
Modification or
Deletion Prior
to Receipt by
the Archive?:**

Lineage

Lineage Statement: Designated observer program office staff generate bimonthly or whenever a turtle interaction was reported by an observer and distributes via email to authorized individuals.

Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID:	22313
GUID:	gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:22313
Metadata Record Created By:	Eric Forney
Metadata Record Created:	2014-09-26 17:22+0000
Metadata Record Last Modified By:	SysAdmin InPortAdmin
Metadata Record Last Modified:	2022-08-09 17:11+0000
Metadata Record Published:	2015-12-03
Owner Org:	PIRO

Metadata Publication Status:	Published Externally
Do Not Publish?:	N
Metadata Last Review Date:	2015-12-03
Metadata Review Frequency:	1 Year
Metadata Next Review Date:	2016-12-03

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Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

